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Four-fold Fields of Quantum Dreams

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SITUATIONAL STATES: PLAY BALL PLAY!

.1 ~ Macro Situation

- We are at Spring Training for the Quantum Baseball team, probably somewhere in the North American Southwest. The Quantum Baseball game itself is the: *“Put me IN to go ON the field(s) Coach, till everyone’s OUT”* part of life.
- We’re at Spring Training at the Institute field satellite office-gym during the OFF-season, because we want to train to get better at being IN, ON, and OUT of the fields, come that actual old ballgame.
- If, and once the season starts as planned, getting IN to the game (e.g. getting OUT of home, ON the road, and into the uniform & park) is a known known; that’s the variability we reduce so that the variability on the field can be fully retained and even augmented. So there is some preparation involved, even before the training begins.
- Sure, for the game itself there are always between 9 and 13 official nestmates on the field plus a bunch of others around. However the total Quantum Baseball environment (in training and in games) is even more multi-agential than that, coinciding without remainder to all things there then and their activities. There are the amateurs who paid to be there (including the disinterested and fanatical), plus all the professionals who were paid to be there (e.g. the infield raking, ticketing, security, livestreaming, managing, catcher in the bullpen, team in dugout).

.2 ~ Micro Situation

- One being present, as a nestmate/teammate and situationally aware, in the Spring Training gym in-between sets, just swapping one perspective at a time and breathing.
- Proximating to the room’s structures as stabilities and dynamics, visually aware within the timecone of an engineered framework (metaphorically provisioned by a [classical holographic representation of a] metal squat rack), paying attention to the design; form and functors.
- In this document the focus is only on some visually-triggered experiences and thoughts (Blake’s “seeing through the eye”), arising during Spring Training in the gym, as one looks at a framework and allows it to effect/affect them.

.3 ~ Big-Screen Replay Of Key Visual-Phenomenological Moment

- Imagine being embodied in a real gym situation as shown on the following page, where the interiority of a visual-metaphorical perspective on a framework was being actualized, analyzed, and utilized (i.e. decomposed into a set of factors) subsequent to a synchrony across the interfacial agent-environment’s boundaries, looking like this:

- To be clearer about the fuzzy instigating situation, focus on the blurry part at upper left:

- Zoom in once more:

- Arguably, this third image (second zooming-in) conveys the necessary and sufficient information for this situation, if there is some sense that the vertical structure in the foreground and the vertical structure out of focus, are somehow related.
- Then, should one assume this relationship to be the case?
 - If yes, then a potential function exists in the GAP BETWEEN (the functor between) the two vertical stabilities.

.4 ~ Preliminary Visual Analysis

- We can fast-forward through/over a lot of the *visual basics* here, such as general and overall aspects of generative models of vision, including the cognitive construction of a hyperbolic uni-perspectival visual field from binocular inputs and other ecological characteristics.
 - The characteristics of a hyperbolic space, leaves a gap between those curved vectors (abstracted edges) to either be retained as-is, or to potentially be filled.
 - If left as gap retained, then the function elicited is more “barrier” like (i.e. “Keep Out!”), and if utilized, then function fulfillment can be served through any number of actions (i.e. very small baseball diamond, change room, place to dry out your uniform, etc.)

- The key to remember here is the **Pre-liminal** of “visual analysis”. Liminal implies *transition* to the one making the observation. In physical terms, one could be passing/crossing a threshold of some type. But the observer is not limited to only the physical. That “pre” aspect could also be constituted as metaphorical when one sees a place to change, as existing within the vertical structures and then labels the area a *change room*.

.5 ~ Primary Implications

- There is a kind of “moon cycle through time”, playing out in space with the perspectival vectors in an instant, representing differential visibility through the framework-as-rack taken from the single visual perspective, looking something like:

- Moon phase visibility, like all other perspectival phenomena and interpretations, are conditioned upon the position/posture/stance and generative model of the “visual fielder”.
- You can move around to get an easy dead reckoning on some vectors (e.g. standing right in front of an eye level hole), of course always at the expense of creating the moon’s full spectrum waxing and waning, no matter where you go.
- There is no view from everywhere/nowhere (but there is every view taken up till now).

.6 ~ Secondary Implications

- There are many GAP-RESPECTING (“as-is” retaining) ways to move through the frame: remotely or visually without a trace (like the camera does when it captures the white on the gym’s back wall), or with a bullet, leaving a pheromone trail, carrying a seed, weaving a thread, etc.

- And, as actually done in gyms around the world, there is a GAP-FILLING (altering) placement of a steel pin, for example to stabilize the UP or DOWN position of a bench, squat, or deadlift. But this “fill” is the opting in (selection) among a series of potential fits.
- Consider this: If a/the framework were totally plugged up (filled, *via positiva*, so no pins could be placed), or had even any welded pins, that would scaffold with fewer potential functions. A trade-off between stability/certainty/rigidity and adjustability affordance, simply exists. The question around what is optimal (alternatives, options or robustness) arises. Except in special, possibly unique cases (where/when a particular channel of arrival is deemed optimal for all) this trading off implication has already been determined by the one fabricating the rack. The implication then is typically resolved by taking/making an assumption around “averages” of the user function.
- Frameworks can almost always be upcycled, or used as scrap metal.

.7 ~ Tertiary Implications

- Where, when, and how the pins are set (or unset) in the framework, means everything for the training exercise. Pinning setups are very dynamic – until set – and then, the stability/continuity of the SET is expected to hold. The positioning of any pins depends on, for example, the exercise and person’s height. One prepares by making adjustments (setting the pins during the warmup sets) and then expects (prefers) that all measures going forward will remain constant, until the next preparation is made. This is the “work” characteristic of frameWORK: stability and adjustability dependent on factors “in play” and filters duly applied and functioning.
 - For example, a primary factor would be does the pin fit the drilled hole(s)? A primary filtering technique would be ensuring that hole alignment across vertical struts generates a level bracing rod outcome.
- Conditioned on the person (the content) and context (e.g. height, choice of rails on or off settings) the necessary preparations of placing pins in safely, strongly, and ergonomically so that they scaffold training: that’s when the framework becomes (after the preparation, and definitely not as a source of initiation) what the framework is for.
 - And that’s essentially WHEN frameworks begin their shift from FORM (only), to (also) FUNCTION. In making “the shift” as action, the space covered between content (agent) and context (envelope) becomes a holding space for Concept(ualization). A framework doesn’t do the work, as much as provide room for work to be done. This is all that frameworks are good for – which is good, because that’s how we need them to be & they are good at/for what they do.
- In the gym we are looking to meet exercisAnts how they are, and take a joint approach that starts with learning-as-postural-strategy and continues on through the learners actual interior cognitive exertion. Our information-as-physical strategic focus (which is also strategic physical-as-information, or *feedback*) in the gym, may be variability-reducing and/ or variability-retaining given the nature or feed-forward and feedback loops coexisting. There can be, and are, aspects of appreciation, assessment, analysis, spotting, co-learning, pre-/post-traumatic care, collaboration, negotiating, strengthening, and so on.

7TH INNING STRETCH

AM Radio: Talk Show Advertisement

Listen up fans. This year, on the ballot, the Gap-Fillers want to pave paradise with facts. They want to festoon the framework, and they want season ticket holders to pay for it. This is no “round the bases, and we’re done” challenge. It’s more like bringing *out* the *in*-field tarps “for your protection” on a sunny day “just in case”. And why? ...So that robots do our big cognitive deadlifts for us?
... Because in times like these there must be an easier way?
...To subsidize our already fairly-priced gym memberships?
... For Active Inference to be the biggest coat-hanger in the world?
Aren’t we in Training for curiosity, capacity-building, and the love of the game?
...To build whole-Tet and multi-Tet quantum strength?
...To be the generators of a little perspiration as a down payment?
...And to make it possible to reach for a (choose your gap here; informational, conceptual, imaginal) canal jump inside-the-mind’er come gametime?
That kind of gap-filling proposal just doesn’t make Epistemic value: Covering up those beautifully plaided mow lines as the in-field (*patterns* established) with plastic, kills the life underneath, as you block the energy from beyond.
...And it doesn’t make Pragmatic value either. Unless of course your version of “covering the bases” is completely misunderstood, and thus becomes a category error.
So do you think it is going to take us all the way, in the Policy Playoffs?
Talk to your family about it at work. Jump twice to find out more. Not financial advice.

AM Radio: 7th Inning Stretch Dialog “Who’s the Exec?”

- A dialog between the Executl’VE (the in-principle commissioner of the league) and the ExecutOR (the frontline workers who operate ON and OFF the field).
- Stage Direction: continue winnerless, dialectical, tragico-comedic dialectical banter of “top-down high road identity OR bottom-up low road function”, until all syndicated commercial breaks are over.

I’VE: “I’VE been tellin’ ya, I’m the Executl’VE”

OR: “OR, I’m telling ya, I’m the ExecutOR”

I’VE: “I’VE been tellin’ ya, who I AM makes me Executl’VE”

OR: “OR, I’m telling ya, the logic of what I DO makes me ExecutOR”

I’VE: “I’VE been tellin’ ya, for me Exec means Executl’VE”

OR: “OR, I’m telling ya, for me Exec means ExecutOR”

END OF STRETCH: BACK TO FINISH THE GAME

.8 ~ Quaternary Implications

- Standing further (moving way back) away from the framework, it is more like the sun's distance to earth, the rays of light are closer to parallel-in-parallax. While further from the framework, it can be better understood amidst other frameworks in the row of squat racks, however, one is more distant from doing bodyweight or barbell exercises at that rack.
 - About intelligence, in the all-seeing case there is a dead reckoning that slices every vector at once, in the all-knowing case all perspectives are taken at once upon one or more reckonings (reflections, re-tellings of happenings that never included a play-by-play), in the all-powerful case the material or imaginary bolt can be struck and unstruck anywhere in a moment, and so on.
 - Closer up to the framework, it is more comprehensible, actionable, and at hand (frame-working assumes a proximity, but not an eclipsing, as given). Also the lines of sight are increasingly variable with respect to postural change, and the moon's static frequency can become extreme and aliased, the closer one gets to the framework.
- For singular embodied organisms and other similarly-perspectival things, the centrality of "When in Doubt: Zoom in, Zoom out" simply cannot be over-esteemed.

.9 ~ Closing Questions and the Final Call

What are Blind Spots, and how are they (re)moved?

- There are Blind Spots no matter where you are, or how you are looking at it: right when you are looking at it and/or in the periphery depending on how you look at it.
- Simply, there are some vectors and holes which are fully eclipsed (totally blocked due to the perspectival angle), and sometimes that is visually on- or off-center.
- That "total eclipse of the prior/observation", is a blind spot for you at that very moment. Moving around with attention, eyes, and body, all are "blind spot removers".

Is the Gym a field? Is the Institute a field?

- No(t only). The Institute is a preserve, enclosing & in feedback with, some built frameworks. There definitely are parts of the preserve that *are* different and multiple fields, and parts that are *like* fields (and also sometimes there is Chris Fields).

Where are Active Inference, Category Theory, Abductive Logic, Identity as dissemination?

- We are not sure how those pillars/pins are deployed, nor what happens then.
- For now it is probably enough to say that: with a Min2(Min2) frame/filter tetralemmal grasp of each of these pillars alone and in all combinations of 1, 2, 3, 4, and more, certainly there are many possibilities here.

And we yield the final Measurement to the Umpire-Bard:

*But thought's the slave of life, and life time's fool;
And time, that takes survey of all the world, Must have a stop.*
— Shakespeare, Henry IV, Part 1, Act V, Scene 4